

LONG-TERM DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN THE FIELD OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Virtual markets have been shown to provide new opportunities for merchants as telecommunications services evolve, combining traditional marketing tools with networked Internet communications and digital marketing techniques. It is proposed that the rapid development of information and communication technologies, the digitalization of the economy, the growth of consumer information culture, increase the presence of enterprises in the virtual space and radically change marketing methods.

Introduction

Telecommunications services allow society to obtain additional channels for the exchange of information. The informatization of society has led to changes in the socio-political sphere of life: interactive television, voting, counting votes in elections via the Internet. It appeared in the field of education thanks to public information.

Possibility of distance learning. The development of telecommunications also led to changes in the labor market: it became possible to work remotely via the Internet. Professions such as stockbroker, programmer, tutor, designer, manager, translator, journalist are available to a wide range of people today.

The telecommunications services market is the "circulatory system" of the entire country's economy. It is the connecting link and the basis of the activities of the state, industry and the consumer sector of the economy. In recent years, there has been a rapid development of the telecommunications market, which is mainly based on innovative achievements in microelectronics and materials science. These achievements can significantly increase the efficiency of information transmission, storage and processing [3].

The growth of telecommunications services may be associated with increased business activity. You can see the relationship between indicators such as the standard of living of citizens and the volume of telecommunications use: the higher the well-being of the population, the greater the volume of services consumed. In addition, we can see an inverse

relationship: the growth of the telecommunications sector leads to an increase in the number of jobs and increased efficiency in other sectors of the economy. Based on this, we can conclude that the telecommunications sector performs infrastructure functions [4].

Research methods

One of the most important aspects of the long-term development of the telecommunications industry is research and innovation-oriented activities, the economic competitiveness of organizations in technological areas important for the economy, requiring thoughtful financial support (primarily for the development of telecommunications infrastructure in remote and hard-to-reach places) necessary to maintain their position.

In turn, ensuring the development of the telecommunications industry according to an innovative scenario requires solving a number of key tasks, including:

- creation of mechanisms to stimulate investment and innovation activities not only of the state, but also of the private sector;

- modernization of enterprise infrastructure telecommunications areas;

- increasing the innovative potential of the telecommunications industry, etc. [5]. In addition, ensuring the long-term innovative development of telecommunication organizations can be complicated by a number of other features of their activities:

- the presence of many stakeholders and participants in corporate relations with different views on the development of the organization;

- influence of government regulators; - significant ramifications of the structure of the telecommunications organization;

- dependence on the infrastructure of large telecommunications organizations, etc.

In this regard, the uniqueness of the innovative development of telecommunications companies can be expressed in the presence of a number of contradictions, which can be defined as the interaction of mutually exclusive factors, interests, ideas and concepts. Such contradictions can be sources of driving forces and growth of an organization or, conversely, hinder its development and cause crisis phenomena [6].

S.G. Vagin revealed in more detail the problem of the influence of contradictions in the activities of communications organizations on their innovative development.

A group of national contradictions is manifested in:

- conflicts of interests of different participants in the innovation process (creators and users of innovative products and technologies) in the value and functional assessment of innovations;

- contradictions between the need to ensure a stable model of production activities and qualitative changes in the company to maintain competitiveness in the long term;

- a conflict between insufficient government support (or lack thereof) and the need to ensure a high level of scientific and technological progress in a telecommunications company.

A group of sectoral (specific contradictions) manifests itself in:

- contradictions between the interests of consumers of communication services and the capabilities of communication organizations, which are represented by a decrease in effective demand while maintaining the need. Obtaining a knowledge-intensive, innovative service, the creation of which requires large expenses;

- the conflict between the demand for certain types of telecommunications services lies in their imbalance between traditional and innovative segments.

Another Russian author who devoted his works to the issues of innovative development of telecommunication organizations is E.P. Zagorodnova believes that the specific features of telecommunications companies determine the decisive role of the innovative management process in the company's activities and the need to integrate this process into the entire management system of telecommunications organizations [8].

Thus, innovative development should be an integral part of the entire management system and strategic development of telecommunications companies. The presence of an effective mechanism for the development of innovations and the further development of innovative development is the most important factor in the sustainability of not only the telecommunications industry, but also of any economic system, the basis of its competitiveness and export potential.

Result and discussion

In the context of global competition, the innovation strategies of key players play a key role in regulating international innovation processes. The introduction of foreign innovative technologies into the domestic market serves to strengthen the position of not only telecommunications companies, but also the state in the global telecommunications complex.

The main areas and projects of research and development of telecommunications companies include:

- LTE standard (expansion and modernization of 4G technologies);
- cloud services (iCloud storage, etc.);
- M2M (eng. "machine-to-machine", "man-to-machine" and "machine-to-mobile" - integration of telecommunications and information technologies to automate business processes and create a more detailed range of services). Such projects include: development of "trackers" (devices for tracking objects at a distance), implementation of projects.

One of the methods of strategic analysis and at the same time systematization of the main trends in the development of a particular industry in the form of weaknesses and strengths, as well as threats and opportunities is SWOT analysis.

As a result of studying the main trends in the development of the telecommunications industry in Russia, a SWOT analysis matrix was created, which includes a description of the weaknesses and strengths, as well as opportunities and threats for the Russian telecommunications industry. In table 5.

- Thus, based on the SWOT analysis, the following directions for the development of the telecommunications market in Russia can be formulated:

- telecommunications technologies can become one of the main factors in increasing the competitiveness of the Russian economy, increasing labor productivity, optimizing management processes, and increasing the overall competitiveness of the national economy;

- the state is the main investor in the comprehensive development of the telecommunications industry;

- In order to ensure the effective functioning of government bodies responsible for the development of the telecommunications sector, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of their interaction with the public and the public. No other area of consumer relations can match the telecommunications industry in terms of diversity, dynamism, pervasiveness and accessibility, making it extremely difficult

to regulate and enforce. The variety of telecommunications services, tariff options and their relative cheapness allow any consumer to create an individual set of necessary services and use them in almost unlimited quantities.

- "Connected car", which has access to the Internet and local network, as well as the distribution of remote control systems for security and production facilities;

-- including information security. cryptographic projects are aimed at developing radio frequency identification tags for various devices, smartphones with a high level of security, mobile systems for remote access control to internal telephone data (Deutsche Telekom).

- e-health standards - standards in the field of medical informatics and healthcare (e-health systems)¹, including such innovative developments as electronic bracelets, mobile routers and remote patient monitoring systems for doctors;

- technologies for communication with clients;

- energy saving [9].

At the same time, there are many complaints from consumers about the quality and reliability of the communication services provided. Everyone complains about interruptions in mobile communications - regardless of which operator provides the service (poor connection, glitches, unclear sound, etc.).

The active growth of the role and role of the service sector in the overall structure of the economy indicates a transition from the industrial stage to the next stage, different from the previous stage of development. Post-industrial society is a society with an economy. The priority has shifted from the production of goods to the production of services, scientific research, the organization of the education system and improving the quality of life.

World experience shows that due to the growing demand for information flows and services, it is necessary to rationally organize access to information and improve the exchange of information between individual subjects of the telecommunications services market.

Another important area of sustainable development of the telecommunications services market is the principle of universal user service. Providing universal service to subscribers with telecommunications services is a generally recognized means of ensuring the use of information and communication resources, ensuring a decent quality of life for the population, as well as equal opportunities for the improvement and development of people [10].

In modern conditions, there is a tendency to adapt to macroeconomic laws in certain socio-economic systems, as well as a tendency for the growth rate of telecommunication services to gradually lag behind the growth rate of general telecommunication services (GTS), which should be higher than the growth rate. The growth of the service sector of the economy (SES) and the latter, in turn, leads to an increase in the growth rate of GDP.

Telecommunications services are part of the infrastructure of society, which is designed to "ensure the transmission of information flows through the use of various forms, types and software means of information transmission, to provide the user with freedom in choosing open services based on data, a set of service capabilities of the service provider (provider) and social and social assistance in the implementation of other opportunities and responsibilities.

In Internet sources, such services are broadcasting, relay or satellite communications, cable systems, transmission of voice data,

images and other information by telephone, telegraph and telex, as well as rental and maintenance services [11].

When considering telecommunications services as a product, the concept of the service bundle model should be used. According to this theory, telecommunication services are described as a collection of different services that make up an overall product that includes basic, ancillary and ancillary services. However, these services have their own characteristics when entering the telecommunications market. Basic and auxiliary services occupy a special place.

The peculiarity of auxiliary services from auxiliary services is that the user cannot refuse them, since in this case the given package will stop working.

Ancillary services are not essential, but their provision is fundamental to highlighting the operating company's competitive advantage. The main service is telephone, Internet, cable TV connection, auxiliary service - customer service, payment methods for services, information materials, etc., auxiliary service - training, equipment, , and others.

In a market economy, there is objectively an imbalance in the relationship between producers-sellers and buyers. It has been determined that the consumer is interested in using the necessary quality services in a certain time interval and with minimal costs for their transmission. And operating companies are interested in selling as many services as possible at high prices. In the context of globalization, telecommunications services have entered the category of basic services. They play an important role in meeting the needs of information flows, as well as in ensuring the development of the economy and society, which indicates the great social importance of these services. This is primarily due to significant structural changes associated with the rapid pace of scientific and technological development and changes in consumer preferences for modern communication services. Existing telephone and mobile cellular services and the Internet are the main product components of the modern telecommunications market.

The difference between natural resources and information resources is that they not only do not dry out, but, on the contrary, increase, develop in quality, and contribute to the rational use of other resources and their conservation. Therefore, the role of the state in the development of the telecommunications industry is very large. In addition, research by individual scientists in the field of macroeconomics has revealed a connection between the economic growth of individual industries (regions) and the state of telecommunications, which indicates the strategic importance of this service sector.

The experience of foreign countries shows that depending on the growth of business activity, the role of the telecommunications sector is significantly expanding. For example, until recently these were service sectors that were designed to serve the needs of business, but gradually they became one of the important components of business, without which business structures cannot function.

The actions of the provider when providing services can affect their quality and, consequently, the cost of using the services. Therefore, the real cost of household services can be determined by three categories: the amount of consumer spending expressed in the price of the service; the time spent searching for any service, represented by its availability; quality of services that can fully satisfy all expectations.

The marketing strategy in telecommunications services enterprises should become an

action program that defines strategic goals and determines the means to ensure the implementation of the chosen development strategy. The success of an enterprise in the near future is determined by how financially coordinated the various areas of its current activities are. Its long-term development and progress will depend on its ability to anticipate changes in the market and adjust its structure and product portfolio accordingly. For such strategic, proactive thinking to be effective, it must be consistent and aimed at “planning for the future,” that is, preparing for actions that will lead to expected results.

Telecommunication services are a set of functions provided to the user by a service provider. In this case, users can select the most suitable service provider (service provider) based on a set of service options[12].

When developing a diversification strategy, it is necessary to take into account the following features of the activities of communication enterprises. These features:

- telecommunication services are aimed at meeting basic needs;
- mutually high elasticity of the volume and price of communication services;
- such as direct communication with the end consumer when organizing telecommunications services.

It is based on the need to use horizontal, vertical and concentric types of diversification when developing the direction of diversification of the marketing strategy of a telecommunications services enterprise. It also focuses on the issuance and sale of stocks and bonds, attracting independent investors and the use of credit resources as forms of attracting financial resources to strategies.

The optimal forms of direction for cooperation in a diversification strategy should be carried out on the basis of an analysis and socio-economic assessment of each option, which includes the following features, namely:

- assessment of the compatibility of a certain type and form of mutual cooperation with the main socio-economic objectives of the enterprise;
- assessment of the economic efficiency of a specific type and form of mutual cooperation of economic entities;
- assessment of the possibilities for implementing each type and form of mutual cooperation between economic entities.

The economic effect of implementing the diversification strategy is ensured by:

- deepening specialization and concentration of production, processing and sale of goods (services);
- use of competitive methods of delivering goods (services) from producers to consumers;
- improving the organization of technological processes that eliminate non-production costs.

The strategic marketing process involves six critical questions. Finding answers to these questions will determine the firm's goals and plan structure accordingly. What does our business look like and what is the company's strategy in this market? What service markets constitute the main market and how to choose a position in these markets? What is the objective attractiveness of the telecommunications market and what opportunities and threats are associated with it? How do the selected strategic objectives translate into the operational marketing mix: product, sales, price and communication?

After a strategic market analysis and answers to six critical questions, the final step is to agree on the chosen goals, the means to achieve them, the action programs to be implemented, and, finally, the list of initial income and expenses for each type of activity and for the enterprise as a whole.

In essence, a strategic marketing plan is a financial plan, but enriched with information about the sources and purposes of financial flows. In practice, it determines the overall economic activity of the enterprise and has a direct impact on all its other functions: IITTI (research and experimental research).

IITTI:

- Market needs must be translated into new, improved or adapted services and products.

Financing:

- The marketing program must take into account financial constraints and resource availability.

Production:

- Limited by sales volume, production capacity and delivery speed.

Human resources:

- Implementation of the plan requires qualified and trained personnel.

The importance of strategic planning in the methodology for developing a marketing strategy is determined by the following additional aspects:

- the plan is a system of values, views of the top management of the enterprise, its goals for the future, which allows you to direct the employees of the enterprise in the right direction;

- the plan describes the initial situation and constraints arising from the environment and its development;

- the plan is a means of coordination, ensures the compatibility of goals with each other and facilitates the achievement of agreement on the basis of objective criteria in the presence of conflicts or contradictions;

- the plan makes it easier to monitor the company's activities and allows for objective interpretation of the differences between goals and results.

Often the strategic plan is complemented by a "contingency plan" that focuses on factors that are vital to the enterprise.

The task of strategic marketing is to always direct and redirect all activities of the company in directions that ensure its development and profitability. Its impulses affect all functions, not just marketing.

Conclusion

Also, the strategic plan must convey the decisions made to those who implement these decisions. This task is complicated by the abstractness of the future. Developing a strategic plan also involves "planning for" unpredictable changes. The purpose of the strategic plan is to provide a clear and consistent description of the chosen strategy for the long-term development of the company. These choices must gradually turn into decisions and programs of action.

The head of any enterprise, even if he is against the idea of planning, is obliged to determine prospects in at least three areas: the necessary investments to adequately adapt to the

evolution of the market or enter new product markets; This depends on the production program, volume of orders, movement of goods, etc. Working capital required to meet financial obligations is calculated based on income and expense targets.

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